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FORMATION OF A METHODOLOGICAL SYSTEM OF ASSIMILATION OF INFORMATION ABOUT TECHNOLOGICAL MACHINES, DEVICES, TOOLS AND MECHANISMS, THE PRINCIPLES OF THEIR OPERATION

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Abstract

The article focuses on the challenges of the “techno-Democratic-Information Society”, the “technology” subject curriculum taught at secondary schools, the expected results in the teaching of this subject, the information to be mastered to students as a component in terms of the realization of the expected results, the theoretical level of the above-mentioned information., the need to establish the regularities of the process of active-interactive training is argued. As a concrete manifestation of the process of forming a methodological system for mastering the principles of work of technological machines, devices, tools and mechanisms, two examples are presented, which include a table for an active-interactive organization.

Keywords: Technological machine, device, tool, mechanism, executive body, engine, transmission, transmission ratio, carrying and carrying pulleys, transmission number.

Relevance of the research topic. In the social, economic, and cultural life of our country, a comprehensive reform program is being implemented that is adequate to the challenges of our time. One of the objectives in choosing education as a priority direction of development in this process is the successful preparation of the emerging young generation for life from an early age. Based on logic, it can be argued that an integral element (an important link) of preparing the younger generation for life, for practical activity is the training of qualified specialists who meet the requirements of the pace of development of our country. This reality was in the center of attention in the “program of reforms in the field of education of the Republic of Azerbaijan”.

Information about technological machines, devices, tools and mechanisms, containing as a component the content of the expected results in the teaching of the subject “Technology”, mandatory for teaching in secondary schools, the principles of which are subordinated to the “immanent function”, is a “cognitive issue of didactic nature” of the formation of a methodological system aimed at its assimilation. This question relates to the problem of system formation, which is broader. This gap is eternal in connection with the development of a system that ensures the implementation of the expected results in the discipline “technology”. Therefore, we affirm the relevance of the topic formulated in the direction of the formation of a methodological system for the assimilation of information about technological machines, devices, tools and mechanisms, the principles of their operation.

Interpretation of materials obtained in the research process.

It is known that the formation of the educational space is based on the paradigm “man - society-

technology (which in the modern period of time becomes adequate to the calls for the IV Industrial Revolution)-nature”, which is a prerequisite for the free development of man or the path of development aimed at civilization. This idea, voiced by us in connection with the formation of the educational space, is not erroneous, since we come to the conclusion that education is a superstructure phenomenon, “education is not life itself, but only readiness for it”[5;203]. Naturally, the education of the present time, by its cognitive (cognitive) nature, can play an increasingly important role in the formation of a person as a person. [5;3]. Today, the successes achieved by Azerbaijan, which has successfully stepped on the path of independence, in the field of education, are formed as a result of a consistent and continuous educational policy. An integrative education system based on democratic, humanistic principles is already being formed in Azerbaijan. In the newly created education, the main factor is considered to be taking into account the parameters of cognitive development, creating its capabilities and conditions [5; 7].

For the first time in the history of education in our country, a curriculum document was developed at the national level in 2006. This document entitled “The Concept of General Secondary Education (National Curriculum) in the Republic of Azerbaijan” is distinguished by the fact that it can serve the formation of personality, the formation of life skills in it, taking into account national and universal values, general development, trends and interests, the creation of favorable learning conditions for all students, built on the principles of relevance, effectiveness and integrativity.[1] subject curricula based on the “concept of general secondary education in the Republic of Azerbaijan”, in particular, the curriculum “technology”

has been developed, which is a conceptual document. Which includes the goals and objectives of the subject, general learning outcomes, content lines, learning standards, teacher and student activities, evaluation principles. In the modern period, when technological progress is gaining momentum, the role of electronic and information technologies is increasing, and competition is increasing every day in a market economy, this document serves to develop the technological thinking of secondary school students, to form their technological skills, to acquire the necessary knowledge to continue education at a later stage.

Generalization of the research materials led us to the conclusion that the assimilation of information about technological machines, devices, tools and mechanisms, the principles of their operation in the implementation of learning outcomes acts as a component that has the function of "assimilation". The expected results in the subject "Technology" at the level of basic education include:

- * independently applies the initial technical and technological knowledge that is considered necessary in life, performs technological work that is important in everyday life, observing safety regulations, makes simple products;

- * develops and implements simple projects, uses them in the manufacture of products;

- * collects and systematizes information about technological processes, uses it in the manufacture of products.[6; 191]

In the process of teaching the subject "Technology", a special place is given to "elements of technology", which are defined as the main parts of the content that the expected results are aimed at. And this further increases the level of accountability of the judgment, which we noted above. This content line provides for teaching students the general characteristics of the equipment they encounter in everyday life, achieving scientific and technological progress, improving production technologies, providing primary information about modern technical devices and structures, mastering relevant skills and skills in this area. Students develop initial knowledge and skills in the field of technology, types and purpose of machines, connection of their parts, layout and requirements for them, mass professions with technology.[6;193].

Through this content line, students get acquainted with the main technological machines, apparatuses, aggregates, tools, their types, structure and principles of work that they encounter in everyday life. Acquiring knowledge about details, mechanisms, household machines, the use of machines in technology, students study the methodology of construction and principles of operation of modern technological equipment and acquire the skills to manage it. All this forms the students' culture of handling technology in everyday life, in the field in which they will work.

This refers to the expected triggers on the content line:

- * Classifies Technological machines, devices and tools;

- *interprets the types, structure and principle of operation of technological machines, draws their kinematic scheme;

- *prepares for work and carries out maintenance of technological machines, devices, devices, tools used in everyday life;

- * interprets the essence of electrical energy, methods of its production, transmission, use, principles of operation of electrical, electronic and automatic devices, devices;

- * uses electronic, radio-electronic, electrical household appliances and demonstrates their maintenance skills.

Nowadays, it is of great importance to instill technological culture in students, which is undeniable. In teaching the subject "technology", the focus should be on dialectical relations between the content line "elements of technology" and the content line "processing technologies", "household culture", "graphics", in other words, one should expect the so-called important condition of the whole-part approach.[6;191]

By the way, we also note that nowadays it is impossible to be content with a narrow specialization. Thanks to his technological skills, a person is able to function in universal production areas. Therefore, laying the primary foundation for the formation of a future generalist in schools is an urgent problem. [8]

In fact, in the process of teaching the subject "Technology" in new socio-economic loyal conditions, the regulation of the environment is aimed at making it easier for students to prepare for independent life, mass and promising professions, acquire generalizing skills and habits, become subjects of readiness on the basis of creative thinking and active activity to adapt to various conditions.

Based on scientific sources and analysis of research materials, our research suggests that in the process of teaching the subject "Technology", the following issues should be brought to the fore:

- a) the formation of polytechnic knowledge and environmental culture;

- b) instilling basic knowledge and skills of household management and family budget;

- c) development of students' independence and ability to solve creative and research tasks;

- d) education of diligence, entrepreneurial collectivism, humanism and humanism, accuracy, correctness, culture, patriotism, culture of behavior and communication.[2]

The technology is constantly being updated and developed. This variable is let s, the invariant is not characteristic. Therefore, every day that has passed, you can meet a new technological development. This development affects a person's life. Innovation and technological development have a positive impact on people's lives. These updates should be the focus of attention in the real pedagogical process. Based on an active educational approach (we consider this approach as a subsystem contained in a perfect learning system) to subjects whose purpose is to provide information about household appliances and their use, machines and principles of their operation, specific technical

machines and equipment, the goal should be studied by selecting appropriate forms and methods, and students should be encouraged to solving cognitive tasks, various analytical and heuristic activities, creative and variable.

The following example of an active lesson, which includes a methodical system of assimilation of information about technological machines, devices, tools and mechanisms, the principles of their work, which are considered a necessity of our life today, cover all spheres of folk art and are used in everyday life, can serve as an example of "system-structure". [2-3; 6-7; 9-10]

Subject:Technology.

Class:VII.

Subject:Information about technological machines and mechanisms.

Standard:2.1.1. Classifies machines, devices and machines, their work explains the principle.

The purpose of the lesson: Recognizes machines, devices and machines, their working principle explains.

Integration:Ad 1.2.4.

Form of work:Work with teams and groups.

Method of work:Brainstorming, discussion, clustering.

Resources: Textbook, worksheets, slides with descriptions of technological machines and mechanisms, electronic calculator, etc,

Motivation: By using the brain attack method, the Class follows

it is addressed with questions:

Questions are asked:

- What do you mean by modern technology?

- What technological equipment do we use in the household?

-What types of transport are there?

-Which machines do you know?

I listen to the students' answers and announce the name of the topic.

Research question:What do you mean by technological machines and mechanisms?

Students' attention is drawn to the textbook. The text is read. Refers to a new lesson as the text is read pp the presentation is demonstrated and the necessary information is given.

Research: Groups are created. Tasks for each group are given on worksheets:

I group- Work in a cluster of household appliances and the importance of each note.

Group II-What is the mechanism? What are the mechanisms? Fill in the table.

Mechanisms types	Application
Strap-on	On the benches
Gear	In drills
Chained	On the bike
Toothed spectacle	On the benches

Group III- What is the transmission number and transmission ratio? What formula is used to calculate the transmission ratio? $D_1 = 60\text{mm}$, $n_2 = 100\text{ cycle/min}$; $n_1 = 90\text{ cycle/min}$ calculate your D_2 if it happens.

Group IV- Work in a cluster of machines and their types, record the information you know about them.

In addition to supervising the work of the groups, the training is interested in the implementation of their work, focusing on the activities of all students in the groups.

Information exchange:

Representatives of each group make a presentation. At the end of the presentations, the participation of other groups with questions is ensured by their participation in the questions of that group. The work of each group is evaluated on the spot.

Discussion and organization of information:

During the discussion, it is acceptable to ask students the following questions:

1. What is the role of machines and mechanisms in the development of technological progress?
2. What types of machines are there?

3. What are the main parts of a technological machine?

4. Is the carpenter's workbench a screw clamp - a mechanism or a machine?

5. Give an example of the mechanisms that differentiate the transmission and change of motion.

6. What formula is used to determine the transfer number?

It is necessary to try to systematize the relationship between the questions asked and the facts and get the answers to the research question.

Conclusion and generalization:

By answering the research questions, students come to the conclusion that technological machines and mechanisms are modern technologies that are widely used in all areas of our lives and the national economy. By learning this topic, children learn that all kinds of

technological machines, which are part of our daily lives, not only make human labor flourish, but also save time, quality products and new information.

As a result, it is necessary to justify the need to study this topic with the help of purposefully selected images.

Creative application:

In order to determine the number of transmissions in the transmission mechanisms, several problems are solved on the board.

Evaluation:

The presentation of each group is discussed at the end and evaluated according to the criteria.

Homework:

Gather information about the latest models of machines and mechanisms.

Scientific novelty of research work. It was determined that the challenges of the modern "techno-democratic-information society" based on the process of forming a methodological system of information about technological machines, devices, tools and mechanisms, the characteristics of the subject curriculum "Technology" taught in secondary schools, results, in terms of the realization of the expected results as a component of the information to be mastered by students, the "opportunity-breaking function", the theoretical level of the information in question, the regularities of the active-interactive learning process.

Practical significance of the research. Relying on the scientific novelty of research work in the activities of practical educators, their activities also provide a basis for the regulation of the environment, which is adequate to address the shortcomings.

The result. 1) Challenges of the modern "techno-democratic democratic-information society" based on the process of forming a methodological system of information about technological machines, devices, tools and mechanisms, mastering their working principles, specific features of the "Technology" subject curriculum taught in secondary schools, expected results in teaching, "opportunity function" in

terms of realization of the expected results as a component of the information to be mastered by students, the theoretical level of the information in question, the regularity of the active-interactive learning process have a positive impact on the effectiveness of adequate real pedagogical process; 2) Facilitates the implementation of the teacher's function of solving the didactic problem related to the organization and management of the learning process - "the formation of the search path in terms of correctly identifying the path leading to the result."

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PROBLEMS ARISING IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF DEEP QUARRIES AND POSSIBLE WAYS OF THEIR SOLUTION

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Abstract

This article presents the mining-geological and hydrogeological features of mineral deposits that significantly affect the efficiency of open-pit mining, as well as the problems that arise in the development of deep pits, and possible solutions are proposed.

Keywords: mining-geological and hydrogeological features of mineral deposits, area of the working zone, rate of lowering of mining operations, length of transport communications, quarry productivity.

During the whole period of operation, deep quarries from the beginning of construction to the completion of mining operations are in continuous development. As a result, the mining conditions change every

year, the depth, the dimensions of the quarry in plan, the area of the working zone, the length of transport communications and other parameters increase. The rate of decrease in mining operations has the greatest